

Terpenoids: Part xxxv. A New Synthesis of β -Elemene

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A new synthesis of β -elemene has been accomplished through the cyclisation of 2,8-dimethyl-5-isopropenyl-undeca-trans-2, 6-diene-1, 10-dibromide with nickel carbonyl in dimethylformamide by the method of Corey and coworkers.

The elemene group of sesquiterpenes confronts an organic chemist with a variety of interesting problems. Various schools¹⁻⁵ have been engaged in the elucidation of the chemistry, structures and biogenesis of these naturally occurring monocyclic sesquiterpenes. The salient features of the structures of this class of hydrocarbons, are the presence of a vinylic group together with an angular methyl on the same carbon atom of the trisubstituted cyclohexane skeleton and two other olefinic bonds which are not in conjugation except in α -elemene represented by the formulation (I). The structures II, III and IV stand for β , γ and δ elemenes respectively.

The main difficulty in devising a clean synthesis of a particular hydrocarbon of this class, is the fixation of these sensitive olefinic bonds in the desired position unambiguously and introduction of the angular methyl group. Recently, Rao and coworkers⁶ have obtained β -elemene(II) and Elemol(V) where in the ethylenic linkages have been executed through pyrolysis which generally involves high temperature. However, in the present

1. V. Sykora, V. Herout, F. Sorm, ; *Collec. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, **21**, 267.
2. S. K. Panikkar, and S. C. Bhattacharyya, ; *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 1509.
3. A. D. Wagh, S. K. Paknikar and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 2647.
4. T. G. Halsall, D. W. Theobald and K. B. Walshaw; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1029.
5. J. H. Gough, and M. D. Sutherland, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 1270.
6. A. S. Rao and L. J. Patil, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 2273.

communication, we report a direct synthesis of β -elemene(II), a constituent of many essential oils, e.g., Sweetflags⁷, Juniper⁷, Orange⁷ and Elecampane.⁸ The present synthesis is designed upon the recent findings of Corey and coworkers⁹ that the formation of a six membered ring (VII) relative to eight and ten membered, is favoured when an acyclic allylic dihalide of the type (VI) is cyclised with nickel carbonyl in a suitable solvent.

For the synthesis of β -elemene, we required the allylic dibromide (XVI) as the cardinal intermediate which would cyclise under the above conditions to the desired hydrocarbon(II). The allylic dibromide (XVI) was procured through the following sequence of reactions as outlined below :

The starting material, ethyl 2-methyl-6,6-ethylenedioxy-2-*trans*-heptenoate¹⁰ (VIII), on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride afforded 2-methyl-6,6-ethylenedioxy-

7. G. L. K. Hunter, and J. L. Parks, *J. Food. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 25.

8. C. C. Asselineau, and J. Asselineau, *Bull. Soc., Chem. de France*, 1957, 1359.

9. E. J. Corey, K. W. Edward, Walt; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2757.

10. O. P. Vig, J. C. Kapur and B. Vig, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).

2-*trans*-hepten-1-ol (IX) in quantitative yields. Equilibration¹¹ of this allylic alcohol with excess ethylvinyl ether in presence of catalytic amount of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate provided the vinyl ether (X) in 80 percent yield. The Claisen rearrangement¹² of the chromatographically pure material, under nitrogen atmosphere, in a sealed tube at 190-195° generated as high as 82 percent yield of the corresponding aldehyde (XI). The ketal-aldehyde (XI) was characterised through its semicarbazone derivative.

The above aldehyde (XI) was submitted to the modified Wittig reaction¹³ with ethyl diethyl phosphonopropionate in presence of sodium hydride using diethyl ether of diethylene glycol as solvent when 2-methyl-5-isopropenyl-8, 8-ethylenedioxy-*trans*-2-nonenolate (XII) was obtained in excellent yield. In view of the fact that the reaction of the phosphonate carbanion with aldehydes tends to be stereospecific and yields only *trans* isomer,^{14,15} so the compound (XII) is given the *trans* configuration at the unsaturated linkage which is further corroborated by the fact that the ketal-ester (XII) showed a single spot on t.l.c. and its I.R. spectrum exhibited a *trans* band at 970 cm⁻¹.

The compound (XII) on deketalisation with dilute hydrochloric acid and acetone afforded ethyl 2-methyl-5-isopropenyl-8-oxo-*trans*-2-nonenolate (XIII) in 64 percent yield. The keto-ester (XIII) on being subjected to modified Wittig reaction¹³ with ethyl diethyl phosphonoacetate under the usual conditions, furnished a mixture of ethyl (2,8-dimethyl-5-isopropenyl)-undeca-*trans*-2-*trans*-8-diene-1, 10-dioate and ethyl (2,8-dimethyl-5-isopropenyl)-undeca-*trans*-2-*cis*-8-diene-1, 10-dioate isomers in which the *trans*-2-*trans*-8 isomer predominates¹⁵. However, no attempt was made to separate the two isomers, as both are expected to give the same final compound β -elemene.

The diester (XIV) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to form the diol (XV) as a viscous liquid which was converted into the corresponding dibromide¹⁶ with PBr₃ in ether. The allylic dibromide (XVI) on cyclisation with nickel carbonyl according to the conditions of Corey and coworkers⁹ was transformed into β -elemene (II).

The synthetic hydrocarbon after chromatography through Florosil column showed a single spot on t.l.c. supporting the fact that both the *trans* and *cis* allylic dibromides on cyclisation with nickel carbonyl yield the same product. The identity of the synthesised product with the natural β -elemene was established by comparison of Infra-red and N.M.R. spectra.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Methyl-6:6-ethylenedioxy-2-hepten-1-ol (IX): To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (2.4 g) in dry ether (160 ml.) was added slowly and with stirring, ethyl 2-methyl-6:

11. A. W. Burgstahler and I. C. Nordin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 198.
12. W. H. Watanabe and L. E. Conlon, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 2828.
13. W. S. Wadsworth and W. S. Emmons, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1733,
D. H. Wadsworth, O. E. Schupp, E. J. Seus and J. Ford, *Org. Chem.*, 1963, **30**, 680.
14. L. D. Bergelson and M. M. Shemyakin, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 149.
15. M. Brown, *J. Org. Chem.*; 1968, **33**, 162.
16. J. M. Osbond, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 5272.

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses are by B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar, Microanalysts of our department. I. R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film.

6-ethylenedioxy-2-*trans*-heptenoate (VIII) (24.0 g.) in ether (60 ml.) at such a rate so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. After the mixture has been stirred for further 2 hr, the contents were decomposed with a saturated solution of sodium sulphate, and extracted with ether. The combined extract was dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) and after the removal of the solvent, the residue on distillation furnished 2-methyl-6: 6-ethylenedioxy-2-hepten-1-ol (IX) (14.0 g.) in 71 percent yield, b.p. $120^\circ/3\text{mm.}$, η^{25}_D 1.4605. (Found: C, 64.32; H, 9.88; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 64.52; H, 9.68). I. R. spectrum absorption bands at 3460 , 1050 cm^{-1} (-OH) and 1065 cm^{-1} (ketal).

2-Methyl-6: 6-ethylenedioxy-2-heptenyl vinyl ether (X): The allylic carbinol (IX) (11.9 g.) was mixed with ethyl-vinyl ether (50 g.) and freshly crystallised mercuric acetate (1.0 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux for 9 hr. The contents were chilled in ice and mixed with sodium carbonate solution (10 percent, 40 ml.) and stirred well for half an hour at 0° . The ether layer was separated and dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography of the residue on alumina (60 g.) furnished on elution with petroleum ether ($40-60^\circ$), the vinyl ether (X) which was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b.p. $90-97^\circ/2-3\text{ mm.}$, yield 9.0 g. (80 percent), $\eta^{24.5}_D$ 1.4685. (Found: C, 67.75; H, 9.72; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.89; H, 9.50). I. R. spectrum absorption bands: 1639 , 1613 , 1190 cm^{-1} (vinyl ether) and 1065 cm^{-1} (-ketal).

3-Isopropenyl-6: 6-ethylenedioxy-heptan-1-ol (XI): The vinyl ether (X) (8.5 g.) was heated for half an hour at $190-195^\circ$ under nitrogen in a fully immersed half filled sealed tube. Direct distillation provided the aldehyde (XI) as a yellow oil, b.p. $115-20^\circ/3-4\text{ mm.}$, yield 7.0 g. (82 percent), $\eta^{24.5}_D$ 1.4660 (Found: C, 67.80; H, 9.61; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.89; H; 9.50). I. R. spectrum absorption bands at 2705 , 1715 cm^{-1} (-CHO), 1065 cm^{-1} (-ketal) and 3060 , 1650 and 890 cm^{-1} ($\overset{\text{R}_1}{\text{R}_2} > \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$).

The semicarbazone of (XI) prepared by the usual method after recrystallisation from ethanol melted at $136-37^\circ$. (Found: N, 15.24; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 15.60)).

Ethyl (2-methyl-5-isopropenyl-8, 8-ethylenedioxy)-*trans*-2-nonenolate (XII): Sodium hydride (1.62 g.) was placed in diethylene glycol dimethyl ether (50 ml.). Ethyl α -diethyl phosphonopropionate (7.8 g.) was added below 20° with stirring and the solution was stirred until gas evolution had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution was then added aldehyde (XI) (6.5 g.) slowly below 10° . After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 1 hr and then heated at 60° on a water bath for half an hour. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with large excess of ice cold water and dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent, the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave 6.0 g. (66 percent) of the unsaturated ester (XII), b.p. $170-75^\circ/15\text{mm.}$, η^{29}_D 1.4490. (Found: C, 68.49; H, 9.46; $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 68.89; H, 9.52). I. R. spectrum absorption bands: 1710 cm^{-1} (α , β -unsaturated ester), 3060 , 1650 , 890 cm^{-1} ($\overset{\text{R}_1}{\text{R}_2} > \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$), 1065 cm^{-1} (-ketal) and 970 cm^{-1} (*trans* double bond).

8-Carboxy-5-isopropenyl-non-7-en-2-one (XIII): The preceding ketal (XII) (5.5 g.) was dissolved in acetone (70 ml.) and mixed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (10 percent, 18 ml.) and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hr. The solution was diluted with brine solution and the product isolated by ether extraction and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent and distillation under reduced pressure afforded the ketone (XIII) (3.0 g.) (64 percent yield),

b.p. 160°/15 mm., η^{29}_D 1.660. (Found: C, 71.83; H, 9.52; $C_{15}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 71.43; H, 9.52). I. R. spectrum absorption bands: 1720 cm^{-1} (a broad band, indicating $-C=O$ and ester), 3060, 1650, 890 cm^{-1} ($\begin{smallmatrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{smallmatrix} > C=CH_2$) and 970 cm^{-1} (*trans* double bond).

Diethyl (2, 8-dimethyl-5-isopropenyl)-undeca-2, 8-diene-1, 10-dioate (XIV): A slurry of 50 percent sodium hydride (0.686 g.) was placed in 1,2-dimethoxy ethane (200 ml.) and ethyl diethyl phosphonoacetate (3.2 g.) was added dropwise at room temperature (20°). After the addition, the solution was stirred until the evolution of gas had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution was then added the ketone (XIII) (4.6 g.) slowly and below 10°. After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 3 hr and then heated on water bath at 60° for half an hour. The product was decomposed with ice-cold water and extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the product was distilled under diminished pressure to yield 4.0 g. of the diester (XIV) in 68 percent yield, b.p. 185-90°/15mm., η^{29}_D 1.4740. (Found: C, 70.81; H, 9.31; $C_{19}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 70.77; H, 9.38). I. R. spectrum absorption bands: 1720 cm^{-1} (-conj. ester), 3060, 1650, 890 cm^{-1} ($\begin{smallmatrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{smallmatrix} > C=CH_2$) and 970 cm^{-1} (*trans* double bond).

2, 8-Dimethyl-5-isopropenyl-undeca-trans-2,8-diene-1, 10-diol (XV): To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.5 g.) in dry ether (50 ml.) was added slowly and with stirring the diester (XIV) (3.5 g.) in ether (25 ml.) at such a rate as to maintain the ether at a gentle reflux. After the mixture had been stirred for another 3 hr, the contents were decomposed with saturated sodium sulphate solution. The product was extracted with ether and dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate). The solvent was removed and residue on distillation under vacuum gave the diol (XV) (1.8 g.) as a thick oily liquid in 58 percent yield; b.p. 170-80°/0.6 mm., η^{29}_D 1.4920. (Found: C, 75.63; H, 10.92; $C_{15}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 75.58; H, 11.00). I. R. spectrum absorption bands at 3460, 1050 cm^{-1} (-OH), 3060, 1650, 890 cm^{-1} ($\begin{smallmatrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{smallmatrix} > C=CH_2$) and 970 cm^{-1} (*trans* double bond).

2,8-Dimethyl-5-isopropenyl-undeca-trans-2, 8-diene-1, 10-dibromide (XVI): The diol (XV) (1.7 g.) in dry ether (60 ml.) was refluxed with PBr_3 (1.42 g.) during 0.5 hours, the solution was stirred and protected from light. The solution was refluxed for 2.5 hours, cooled, poured in ice-water, shaken and extracted with ether. The extract was combined, washed with saturated solution of sodium hydrogen carbonate and water (twice) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was removed and the bromide was used directly.

1-Methyl-1-vinyl-2, 4-di-isopropenylcyclohexane (β -elemene, II): The above allylic dibromide (1.5 g.) dissolved in dimethyl formamide (4.5 ml.) was slowly introduced, *via* a syringe, to a solution of nickel carbonyl (0.7 g.) in dimethyl formamide (160 ml.) under argon at 50°. During the addition, a deep-red colour appeared and at the end it faded and gave way to the characteristic green colour of nickel-II bromide in dimethyl formamide. The solvent was removed under diminished pressure and the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was filtered through florosil column (elution with n-hexane). This was purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b.p. 118-23°/15 mm. T. L. C. showed a single visible spot (n-hexane: benzene :: 1 : 1). η^{28}_D 1.4932 (reported¹ η^{29}_D 1.4935). (Found: C, 88.11;

H, 11.64°; C₁₃H₂₄ requires, C, 88.23; H, 11.77)). The infra-red spectrum of the synthesised hydrocarbon was found to be identical with that of naturally occurring hydrocarbon. The synthetic hydrocarbon was further confirmed by its N.M.R. spectrum which showed characteristic signals at T 3.98, 4.28, 4.4 (1H, CH = CH₂), 5.0- 5.34 (6H, -CH = CH₂, C = CH₂), 8.34 (6 H, \gg C-CH₃) and 9.01 (3H, $\overline{\overline{\vee}}$ CH₃).

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